

A Monthly e Magazine
ISSN:2583-2212

Jan 2024 Vol.4(1), 278

Popular Article

Environmental Pollution: A threat to life in the air

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Air pollution is now considered to be the world's largest environmental health threat, accounting for 7 million deaths around the world every year. Air pollution causes and exacerbates a number of diseases, ranging from asthma to cancer, pulmonary illnesses and heart disease.

Air pollution is contamination of the indoor or outdoor environment by any chemical, physical or biological agent that modifies the natural characteristics of the atmosphere. Air quality is closely linked to the earth's climate and ecosystems globally. Many of the drivers of air pollution (i.e. combustion of fossil fuels) are also sources of greenhouse gas emissions. Household combustion devices, motor vehicles, industrial facilities and forest fires are common sources of air pollution. Pollutants of major public health concern include particulate matter, carbon monoxide, ozone, nitrogen dioxide and sulfur dioxide.

5 ways to limit breathing polluted air

1. Limit walking on busy streets during rush hour and if you have a young child with you, try to lift them up above the level of vehicle exhausts.
2. Limit spending time at specific hotspots of traffic such as cars stopped at traffic lights.
3. When you are doing physical activity outdoors, try exercising in less polluted areas.
4. Limit the use of cars in highly polluted days
5. Don't burn waste as the smoke that results damage our health

